

① Why does DDC 16 edition is called Phoenix schedules?

⇒ From the 2nd to the 14th editions DDC always inserted new topics and expanded, but did not alter the places of subjects. Such alternations would require libraries to reclassify, and DDC may have disfavoured reclassification.

However, expansion and development without relocation (or-allocation) of classes made the scheme look antiquated and too bulky in some parts. So with the 15th (1951) and the 16th (1958) editions relocation of subjects became a special feature.

Besides relocations, DDC started from its 16th ed. complete revision of the schedules for certain subjects in order to cope with the latest development of such subjects. These completely-revised schedules are now called Phoenix schedules. In a Phoenix schedule only the basic number of the discipline or subject is certain to remain the same as in previous editions, all other being freely reused

to the extent required. In the 16th ed. the phoenix schedules were for Inorganic Chemistry and organic Chemistry; in the 17th ed. psychology, and in the 18th ed. Law and mathematics got phoenix schedules. In the 19th ed. there are phoenix developments for sociology, political process, and British local administrative units.

② Why DDC index is called Related index?

⇒ The alphabetical index to a book Classification should be what in DDC is called 'Relative Index'. The very nature of book Classification demands the index to be of such a character. Book Classification is not a pure scientific classification. Scientific classification tends to be taxonomic (e.g., Botanical or Zoological Classification) and as such it isolates entities or phenomena and allocates them unique or single places in the scheme. But a Book Classification, as we have said, is aspect classification in which an entity or a phenomena is called classed

According to the subject-contexts or aspect it is considered. And the Subject-Contexts or aspect being usually many, a term in the index gets several or many entries, that is location references. So the Relative Index registers a term representing a subject or entity used in a scheme and brings under it all the aspects from which the subject or entity has been considered and the respective class numbers of the aspects. By doing this job the relative index provides what J. Mills has called a supplementary classification; ~~thereby~~ thereby attempting to reduce the defect of a classification which cannot bring together all the aspects and relations of a topic in the systematic arrangement.

We give an example from the relative index to DDC:

Egg

and Nutrition, physiological 612.39283

as food, Domestic economy 614.12

-hygiene 613.28

Cookery 614.665

Eastern folklore 398.33212

Ornithology 598.2

painting medium 751.242

poultry farming 636.513